

Learners' Reading Comprehension Skills

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Abstract:

Reading comprehension is crucial for success and effective functioning in modern society. Understanding what is being read entails not just comprehending the content but also comprehending it thoroughly. This study aimed to determine the level of learners' reading comprehension skills in a medium-sized division in the Central Philippines for the school year 2023-2024. This study specifically answered the following questions: 1) the reading comprehension skill level in identifying the main idea or noting details; answering direct recall questions; making inferences; drawing conclusions; sequencing events; and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary; 2) the learners' reading comprehension level when grouped according to the abovementioned variables; 3) the significant difference in the level of learners' reading comprehension skills when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables. This study employed the descriptive research design, specifically a descriptive approach. Purposive sampling procedures were adopted. The learners' reading comprehension was "frustration," which means that readers found reading materials so tricky that they could not successfully respond to the text, also means they are struggling to achieve a basic level of comprehension when reading texts. These findings underscore the importance of the teacher's role to develop and provide regular opportunities for students to practice reading aloud to improve fluency and articulation. Also, various stakeholders allocate funds to promote literacy programs and initiatives in local schools, such as reading materials and teacher professional development.

Keywords: Reading Comprehension, Identifying the Main Idea or Noting Details; Answering Direct Recall Questions; Making Inferences; Drawing Conclusions; Sequencing Events; and Identifying unfamiliar vocabulary

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Learning to read is one of the most crucial outcomes of primary education, essential for children's broader literacy skills and future participation in society, including the workforce (DepEd, DM No. 173 s. 2019). Reading serves various purposes, such as pleasure or acquiring information. Mason et al. (2012) state that reading comprehension is vital for success today, requiring a thorough understanding of the content. An (2013b) describes the skills, knowledge, and methods needed to grasp a text, utilizing the reader's prior experiences or schemas.

To be effective in comprehension, the reader must have fluent word identification abilities. It is critical that word identification becomes automatic and only needs the reader to exert excessive effort (Roembke et al., 2019). According to Kotzer et al. (2021), reading comprehension is a linguistic skill that relies on a decoding and literal understanding of the text.

In one of the schools of a medium-sized division in Central Visayas, Philippines, the reading profile of the Grade 8 learners based on the Microsoft Teams Reading Progress Assessment used the Phil-IRI tool showed seven learners belong to independent readers, 13 for instructional readers, two learners belong to frustration readers, and 8 for non-readers. The fact that few 8th-grade learners could read independently and with the presence of non-readers exemplified this issue.

As a school head of the researched venue, the researcher encountered the problems mentioned above during the comeback of face-to-face classes. Thus, this research was conducted to determine the level of learners' reading comprehension skills of Grade 8 learners in the school year 2023-2024. The results of this study served as the basis for an intervention to boost their reading abilities and pave the way for progress in their academic performance.

Current State of Knowledge

Reading comprehension abilities are essential for growth. Additionally, a lack of reading comprehension indicates poor reading. Besides, the primary goal of reading is to gather information from the material being read. To do so,

the reader must be able to interact with the script to elicit meaning from it correctly (Alfani, 2014, as cited by Asst, 2016).

Al-Qahtani (2016) as cited by Alenezi (2021) reading problems and difficulties dominate mainstream teaching techniques, such as an unsupportive learning atmosphere, lack of explicit strategy-based instruction, and lack of enthusiasm and motivation for reading.

As emphasized by Mirasol (2019), the reader's vocabulary size and reading motivation are two factors that influence learners' reading comprehension. Furthermore, students also considered the teaching and the learning environment. The development of a healthy reading attitude in a student begins at home since this is where literacy awareness begins. Reading motivation, or simply motivation, is cultivated and reinforced at home.

According to Johnson and Johnson (1989), as cited by Marzban and Akbarnejad (2012), more reading comprehension when students participate in cooperative learning, they acquire more control over their learning and social connections with peers. Additionally, in cooperative learning teaching, teachers play the position of coach, guide, or facilitator rather than knowledge teller.

Jennifer P. (2020), to grasp what is being said, students must apply their underlying oral language understanding. Furthermore, while some learners may be able to decode all of the words on a page, understanding will only occur if their underlying language system is established.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study was anchored on Ausubel's Schema Theory of Reading in 1918. The essential assumption of this theory is that the meaning does not lay alone in the text but interacts with the cognitive structure or schemata that already exist in the reader's mind Karami and Khajavi (2021). These "schemata" represent, in Ausubel's (1918) terms, the "ideational scaffolding" or the framework for understanding new information. According to Rummelhart and Ortony (1977), schema represents generic concepts stored in memory. A specific idea is stored by recognizing the characteristics of the event that are connected to other previously recorded concepts rather than remembering that isolated event in its entirety and its most basic components. One relates the information in the text to what has been already known.

Furthermore, a reader's understanding of a printed message is impacted by their background and history, knowledge, and beliefs, all of which are used to form schemata that give the interpretive framework for interpreting discourse. Prior knowledge can have such an impact that a reader perceives just one interpretation of a text despite numerous viable interpretations. Schemata are crucial for making inferences and predictions and searching memory for previously read material to reconstruct meaning.

Schema theory is essential to this study as it emphasizes using the reader's preexisting knowledge and experience, setting purposes for reading, and asking relevant questions before and after reading.

This theory also covers other critical skill areas, such as speaking and listening, as this allows the search for previously learned areas and reconstructing their meaning. Teachers play an essential role in students' reading comprehension. Teachers must know how to assist students in setting up a cognitive structure. The teacher would help learners develop new schemata and establish connections between them.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of learners' reading comprehension skills in a medium-sized division in the Central Philippines for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it aimed to determine: 1) the reading comprehension skill level in identifying main idea or noting details, answering direct recall questions; making inferences; drawing conclusions; sequencing events; and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary; 2) the learners' reading comprehension when grouped according to demographics; and 3) the significant difference in the level of learners' reading comprehension skills when grouped according to demographics.

Methodology

This section presents the methodology of the study. It discusses the research design, study locale, subject, and the participants. This data-gathering procedure includes the research instrument and the test of its validity and reliability, the data-processing procedure, the analytical schemes, and the statistical tools.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design to determine the level of reading interest of 8th-grade learners in their reading comprehension skills in a selected school situated in a medium-sized division in the Central Philippines for the school year 2023-2024.

The descriptive research method provided a way to describe the nature of the situation as it existed at the time of the study. A descriptive study approach is excellent for investigations that seek to discover what is currently happening regarding relationship-held ideas and beliefs, processes and outcomes, and emerging trends. Descriptive research entails describing, recording, analyzing, and interpreting the current native composition of a phenomenon's process (Manuel & Medel, 2076).

Descriptive research entails acquiring data that characterizes occurrences and organizing, tabulating, depicting, and describing the data. Descriptive research is also valuable in providing facts on which scientific judgment may be based upon assessing the present study. According to Dudovsky (2017) as cited by North South Business Review (2020), descriptive research is also helpful in supplying information for scientific judgment based on the current investigation.

Descriptive research designs are also valuable in gaining essential knowledge about the present situation of the study. It is possible to generate a suggestion based on enhanced data (Massy, 2015).

Hence, this research design was appropriate for this study as it intends to collect current data, like the learners' reading comprehension skills. The data acquired were used to formulate expert assessments and conclusions.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were 34 grade 8 students in a medium-sized division in the central Philippines, comprising 20 boys and 14 girls. Purposive sampling procedures were adopted, considering there were just a few responders. Purposive sampling is a non-random selection strategy in which researchers deliberately choose individuals who might offer relevant and valuable answers to the study questions.

Instruments

The researcher gathered the needed data for this study by constructing a researcher-made survey questionnaire and the pre-validated reading selection culled from the Philippine-Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) 2018 manual to determine the level of reading interest of the grade 8 learners in the medium size division in the central Philippines. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part I dealt with the demographic profile of respondents in terms of sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and number of siblings. Part II of the instrument contained the reading selections with ten questions that measured the level of reading comprehension skills in the following areas: identifying the main idea or noting details, answering direct recall questions, making inferences, drawing conclusions, sequencing events, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. The following were the interpretations: Excellent (4.21 – 5.00); Very Good (3.41 – 4.20); Good (2.61 – 3.40); Fair (1.81 – 2.60); Poor (1.00 – 1.80). The results yielded 4.74 with an interpretation of (excellent). The KR-20 guidelines Reliability Interpretation is the following: 0.90 and above (excellent), 0.80-0.90 (very good), 0.70-0.80 (good), 0.60-0.70 (somehow low), 0.50-0.60 (suggest revision) and .50-below (questionable). The results yielded 0.87 with an interpretation of (Good), indicating that it is acceptable.

Procedure

Official letters of authorization asking permission and cooperation to collect data from the target responder were addressed to the principals of the schools and the superintendent of the Schools Division (SDS) in order to gather the data. After the study instrument was authorized, the researcher scheduled its administration to minimize disruption and to ensure readiness. Teachers and the administration assisted in administering the instrument in person utilizing hard copies. Every piece of data gathered for this research was kept private. After obtaining the survey questionnaire, the gathered data were forwarded to a statistician for tabulation, analysis, and tabular presentation of the results. Appropriate statistical procedures were used to the problem.

Data Collection

To collect the data, official letters of authorization were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) and school principals, requesting their approval and cooperation to collect data from the target respondent. To avoid inconvenience and to invoke preparedness, the researcher planned the administration of the study instrument once approved. The instrument was administered face-to-face using hard copies, with the help of teachers and the principal. All information collected for this study was kept confidential. Following retrieving the survey questionnaire, the collected data were sent to a statistician for tabulation, application of suitable statistical methods to the problem, analysis, and presentation of the results tabularly.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as a statistical tool to measure the central tendency to describe the condition of the things under investigation.

Objective 2 also used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as statistical tool to determine the level of learners' reading comprehension skills when grouped according to the abovementioned demographics.

Objective 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and independent T-test to determine whether or not there was a significant difference in the level of learners' reading comprehension skills when grouped according to the same demographics.

Ethical Consideration

The study assured respondents they voluntarily participated in the survey by granting consent to complete the data entry with optional information. For anonymity, the researcher agreed not to share the participants' identifying information with anybody who was not directly involved in the study. Furthermore, the information acquired from this survey is completely secure and was not utilized for any other reason than this study.

Results and Discussion

This section the data gathered were further treated, presented, analyzed, and interpreted to focus on the specific problems of the study.

Reading Comprehension Skills based on Selected Constructs

Table 1

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills according to Identifying the Main Idea or Noting Details, Answering Direct Recall Questions, Making Inferences, Drawing Conclusions, Sequencing Events, and Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
Identifying the Main Idea or Noting Details	51.47	Frustration Level
Answering Direct Recall Questions	44.42	Frustration Level
Making Inferences	39.71	Frustration Level
Drawing Conclusions	58.53	Instructional Level
Sequencing Events	22.65	Frustration Level
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	2.06	Frustration Level
Overall Mean	36.47	Frustration Level

Table 1 presents the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying the main idea or noting details, answering direct recall questions, making inferences, drawing conclusions, sequencing events, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 36.47%, which is interpreted as "Frustration Level" for their level of reading comprehension skills, which generally implies that the individual has a basic understanding of the text but may struggle with more complex or nuanced aspects. They can grasp main ideas and some details but may require additional support or effort to comprehend certain materials fully.

However, when examined more closely, the respondents had the highest mean in conclusion, with 58.53% interpreting it as "Instructional level." They had the lowest mean in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, with a total mean of 2.06%, regarded as a "frustration level." This implied that respondents lack experience with the language, have cognitive impairments, and are unfamiliar with the topic matter. Learners from the research venue received the lowest scores in identifying unfamiliar words for a variety of reasons – as being frustrated readers, they do not have enough time to study due to household chores, their homes are far from school, they have limited time to study their notes, they cannot even ask their parents for assistance due to limited capabilities, and they have limited financial resources.

Meanwhile, teachers can use a variety of strategies to assist students in identifying unfamiliar words, including reading aloud to the students and discussing unfamiliar words as they arise in context; engaging students in fun activities such as word puzzles and vocabulary bingo; teaching students how to break words down into prefixes, roots, and suffixes to understand their meaning, and instructing students on how to use dictionaries effectively to look up unfamiliar words. Graphic organizers such as ideas maps or semantic webs may also be used by the teachers to display word connections and meaning visually.

This result is supported by the findings of Quigley (2018) that the most popular tactics for understanding a new or unfamiliar word are utilizing a dictionary or estimating the word's meaning based on the context of the phrase. In the study of Ali (2020), teachers can help pupils improve their language acquisition abilities by assigning exercises like guessing socially relevant facts.

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills Based on Selected Constructs and Groupings by Sex

Table 2

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills according to Identifying Main Idea or Noting Details, Answering Direct Recall Questions, Making Inferences, Drawing Conclusions, Sequencing Events, and Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary when Grouped according to Sex

Areas	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Identifying Main Idea or Noting Details	49.00	Frustration Level	55.00	Frustration Level
Answering Direct Recall Questions	43.00	Frustration Level	46.43	Frustration Level
Making Inferences	38.00	Frustration Level	42.14	Frustration Level
Drawing Conclusions	52.00	Frustration Level	67.86	Instructional Level
Sequencing Events	18.00	Frustration Level	29.29	Frustration Level
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	2.00	Frustration Level	2.14	Frustration Level
Overall Mean	33.67	Frustration Level	40.48	Frustration Level

Table 2 reveals the data on the reading comprehension skills when grouped according to sex. Male respondents assessed an overall mean of 33.67%, interpreted as "frustration level," and female respondents assessed an overall mean of 40.48%, interpreted as "frustration level." However, in a deeper look at each item, male respondents have assessed the highest rating of 52.00% on drawing conclusions interpreted as "frustration level." They had the lowest mean in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, with 2.00% interpreted as "frustration level." In comparison, the female category has the highest mean in conclusion, with 67.86% interpreted as "instructional level," and the lowest mean is in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, with 2.14% interpreted as "frustration level." This means that both males and females scored lowest in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary.

Furthermore, the result implied that males and females could comprehend the content somewhat but may need more depth than a greater skill level. However, when looked deeper, male respondents got the lowest mean compared to females in identifying unfamiliar words.

The male group got the lowest score in identifying unfamiliar words for some reason; most were not focused – manifesting in a lack of interest, engaging in online games, and sparing no time for developing reading habits. Teachers may aid in this by engaging male students in differentiated instruction to meet their unique requirements and giving them additional support or challenges based on individual competency levels and learning styles.

Another support from the study by Latham et al. (2015) revealed that the progress of students who received differentiated instruction over multiple years had consistently outperformed their peers in comprehension and academic achievement.

Lastly, according to Miller and Halpern (2014), societal expectations and gender norms may impact how males and females interact with language; boys may receive less encouragement or chances to improve vocabulary skills than girls, resulting in disparities in vocabulary knowledge.

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills according to Selected Constructs and Groupings by Educational Attainment

Table 3

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills according to Identifying Main Idea or Noting Details, Answering Direct Recall Questions, Making Inferences, Drawing Conclusions, Sequencing Events, and Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary when grouped according to Parents' Educational Attainment

Areas	Lower Mean		Higher Mean	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Identifying Main Idea or Noting Details	48.50	Frustration Level	55.71	Frustration Level
Answering Direct Recall Questions	43.50	Frustration Level	45.71	Frustration Level
Making Inferences	41.00	Frustration Level	37.86	Frustration Level

Drawing Conclusions	53.00	Frustration Level	66.43	Instructional Level
Sequencing Events	16.50	Frustration Level	31.43	Frustration Level
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	1.50	Frustration Level	2.86	Frustration Level
Overall Mean	34.00	Frustration Level	40.00	Frustration Level

Table 3 shows the statistics on reading comprehension skills when grouped by parents' most outstanding educational level. Respondents from the lower (Elementary level) group have an aggregate mean of 34.00%, defined as a "frustration level." Respondents with higher education levels (high school and beyond) had an overall mean of 40.00%, assessed as a "frustration level." This means that the respondents from lower and higher educational attainment have both interpretations of "frustration level." However, when looking deeper into the results in the lower group, the drawing conclusions had the highest mean, with 53.00% interpreted as "frustration level," and the lowest mean in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, with 1.50% interpreted as "frustration level." While in the higher group, the drawing conclusion had the highest mean of 66.43%, interpreted as "instructional level," the lowest mean in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, with 2.86% interpreted as "frustration level."

As an analysis, parents with lower educational attainment (e.g., at the elementary level) got the lowest mean in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary compared to parents with the highest educational attainment. It implied that the learners' ability to understand and interpret text is moderate, considering the academic background of their parents. Their parent's level of education also influences the learners' comprehension. While they can interpret the text to some extent, their comprehension may be weaker than that of learners with parents who have attained higher levels of education.

Teachers play a vital role in assisting learning achievement in this aspect. One way is to provide accessible resources and materials that parents use to support their children's learning at home, organize informal sessions that can cover strategies to encourage positive study habits, and offer individualized support and guidance to parents who may feel intimidated or unsure about how to help their children academically and recognize and celebrate parent parents' effort.

The result of the study is supported by Murro et al. (2023), who state that parents with poor educational attainment need to explain, elaborate, and comprehend the teachings; they cannot assist and meet the learner's needs.

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills according to Selected Constructs and Groupings by Average Family Monthly Income

Table 4

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills according to Identifying Main Idea or Noting Details, Answering Direct Recall Questions, Making Inferences, Drawing Conclusions, Sequencing Events, and Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary when grouped according to Average Family Monthly Income

Areas	Lower	Interpretation	Higher	Interpretation
	Mean		Mean	
Identifying Main Idea or Noting Details	45.63	Frustration Level	56.67	Frustration Level
Answering Direct Recall Questions	41.25	Frustration Level	47.22	Frustration Level
Making Inferences	38.75	Frustration Level	40.56	Frustration Level
Drawing Conclusions	48.75	Frustration Level	67.22	Instructional Level
Sequencing Events	18.13	Frustration Level	26.67	Frustration Level
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	1.88	Frustration Level	2.22	Frustration Level
Overall Mean	32.40	Frustration Level	40.09	Frustration Level

Table 4 shows the statistics on reading comprehension skills when grouped according to the average family monthly income. Respondents from lower income have an overall mean of 32.40%, defined as "frustration level." Respondents with higher income have an overall mean of 40.09%, evaluated as a "frustration level." Both respondents from lower and higher family incomes have the same interpretation of "frustration level." Still, when looking at the data closely, respondents from lower family incomes got the highest mean in concluding with 48.75"

interpreted as "frustration level," and the lowest mean in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary with 1.88% interpreted as "frustration level." For the higher income group had the highest mean in concluding with 67.22% interpreted as "instructional level" and had the lowest mean in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary with 2.22% interpreted as "frustration level."

The respondents from lower-income families struggled most with identifying unfamiliar vocabulary due to limited exposure to language and restricted access to books, educational materials, and enrichment activities. Parents with low incomes may need more time and energy. The said respondents became reluctant in day-to-day activities in school for various reasons: lack of food, vitamin-deficient meals, insufficient sleep, and a lack of motivation. In this regard, the teacher may help by forging partnerships between schools and the community. Most instructional materials are distributed to students, and home visits are conducted for follow-up and consultations.

To conclude, family income can play a role in providing access to resources and educational opportunities. Chen et al. (2018) illustrated the complicated linguistic mechanisms in the link between parental socio-economic position and students' reading ability.

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills according to Selected Constructs and Groupings by Number of Siblings

Table 5

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills according to Identifying the Main Idea or Noting Details, Answering Direct Recall Questions, Making Inferences, Drawing Conclusions, Sequencing Events, and Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary when grouped according to the Number of Siblings

Areas	Few	Interpretation	Many	Interpretation
	Mean		Mean	
Identifying Main Idea or Noting Details	60.77	Instructional Level	45.71	Frustration Level
Answering Direct Recall Questions	46.92	Frustration Level	42.86	Frustration Level
Making Inferences	46.15	Frustration Level	35.71	Frustration Level
Drawing Conclusions	64.62	Instructional Level	54.76	Frustration Level
Sequencing Events	27.69	Frustration Level	19.52	Frustration Level
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	3.08	Frustration Level	1.43	Frustration Level
Overall Mean	41.54	Frustration Level	33.33	Frustration Level

Table 5 displays statistics on reading comprehension skills when grouped by the number of siblings. Respondents with a small number of siblings have an overall mean of 41.54%, evaluated as a "frustration level." In contrast, respondents with many siblings (4 or more) have an overall mean of 33.33, defined as "frustration level." But, when looking closely at the data in the few categories, the identifying main idea or noting details had the highest value, with 60.77% interpreted as "instructional level," and had the lowest value in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, with 3.08% interpreted as "frustration level." In many categories, the drawing conclusion has the highest value, with 54.76% defined as "frustration level," and the lowest value in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, with 1.43% defined as "frustration level."

The result implied that the respondents from minor siblings could provide opportunities for diverse perspectives, social interactions, comparative analysis, supportive learning environments, and personal connections, ultimately contributing to their ability to comprehend and interpret a wide range of text effectively. On the contrary, the respondents from a large family would prioritize individual needs, considering the emotional support and encouragement of the siblings are given priority.

Looking closely at the data, respondents from a family with more than four siblings got the lowest mean. In more prominent families, having less one-on-one care, parents may have less time and attention to spend on each learner individually and less time spent engaging in literacy-related activities, which are critical for vocabulary development. Teachers may aid by offering remedial reading sessions and one-on-one reading tutorials and letting them participate in exciting activities such as daily word unlocks and diary entries.

Keller (2015) discovered that the more siblings a child has, the poorer their second language proficiency, mediated by attendance at early education institutions. Lastly, Prime et al. (2014) showed that children with larger sibships had greater receptive vocabulary levels than their next-in-age older siblings.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills Identifying the Main Idea or Noting Details when grouped and compared according to Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, and Average Family Monthly Income

Table 6

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills Identifying the Main Idea or Noting Details when grouped and compared according to Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, and Average Family Monthly Income

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	20	49.00	-0.931	0.362	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	14	55.00				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	20	48.50	-1.183	0.247	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	55.71				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	16	45.63	-1.900	0.068	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	18	56.67				
Number of Siblings	Few	13	60.77	3.056	0.005	0.05	Significant
	Many	21	45.71				

Table 6 shows the statistics on the significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying the main idea or noting details when grouped and compared according to sex. As shown in Table 8, for variable sex, the computed t-value is --0.931 with a p-value of 0.362, more significant than the 0.05 significance level, and thus interpreted as "no significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying main idea or noting details when grouped and compared according to sex" is accepted.

For the parents' highest educational attainment variable, the computed t-value is -1.183, with a p-value of 0.247, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying main idea or noting details when grouped and compared according to parents' highest educational attainment" is accepted.

For the average family monthly income variable, the computed t-value is -1.900, with a p-value of 0.068, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying main idea or noting details when grouped and compared according to family monthly income" is accepted.

However, for the variable of the number of siblings, the computed t-value is 3.056, with a p-value of 0.005, which is less than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying main idea or noting details when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings" is not accepted.

Examining further into the data on identifying foreign words, it is discovered that the variable with the lowest p-value denoted the number of siblings. This implied that the identifying main idea or noting details of the learners' reading comprehension skills differed as rated by respondents when compared to the number of siblings. This is because larger families with more siblings may experience increased competition for attention and resources, potentially affecting individuals' ability to concentrate on reading tasks and develop effective comprehension strategies. Also, larger families may face challenges allocating resources such as books, educational materials, and quiet study spaces.

Teachers offer reading materials and educational resources, assigning classmates who can tutor during the vacant time, oral remedial classes, and peer tutoring.

Knoester and Plikuhn (2016) revealed that siblings almost always impact our participants' literacy lives, including exchanging reading materials, modeling reading, discussing books, providing reading resources, and using siblings as teachers.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Answering Direct Recall Questions when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Table 7

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Answering Direct Recall Questions when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	20	43.00	-0.585	0.584	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	14	46.43				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	20	43.50	-0.412	0.683	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	45.71				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	16	41.25	-1.090	0.285	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	18	47.22				
Number of Siblings	Few	13	46.92	0.809	0.424	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	21	42.86				

Table 7 shows the statistics on the significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in answering direct recall questions when grouped and compared according to sex. As shown in Table 9, for variable sex, the computed t-value is -0.585 with a p-value of 0.564, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level and thus interpreted as "no significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in answering direct recall questions when grouped and compared according to sex" is accepted.

For the parents' highest educational attainment variable, the computed t-value is -0.412, with a p-value of 0.683, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in answering direct recall questions when grouped and compared according to parents' highest educational attainment" is accepted.

For the average family monthly income variable, the computed t-value is -1.090, with a p-value of 0.285, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in answering direct recall questions when grouped and compared according to family monthly income" is accepted.

For the variable of the number of siblings, the computed t-value is 0.809, with a p-value of 0.424, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in answering direct recall questions when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings" is accepted.

Taking a closer look at the facts in answering direct recall questions, the respondents in the variable, the average family monthly income, had the lowest p-value. This implied that the average family's monthly income can impact learners' ability to answer direct recall questions. Learners with lower family incomes have limited access to educational resources such as books and technology. Lower-income learners may need help to afford nutritious food and have limited access to healthcare. Poor nutrition can negatively impact cognitive function, including memory, making it more difficult for individuals to recall information questions. The teacher in the research venue offered and supported learners struggling with reading comprehension by providing them with reading intervention, giving reading materials, and engaging learners in fun activities.

According to Leonard et al. (2015), children from low-income families demonstrated poorer working memory performance than those from higher-income families.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Making Inferences when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Table 8

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Making Inferences when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	20	38.00	-0.464	0.647	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	14	42.14				

Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	20	41.00	0.333	0.742	Not Significant
	Higher	14	37.86			
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	16	38.75	-0.208	0.837	Not Significant
	Higher	18	40.56			
Number of Siblings	Few	13	46.15	1.179	0.249	Not Significant
	Many	21	35.71			

Table 8 shows the statistics on the significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in making inferences when grouped and compared according to sex. As shown in Table 10, for variable sex, the computed t-value is -0.464 with a p-value of 0.647, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level and thus interpreted as "no significance." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in making inferences when grouped and compared according to sex" is accepted.

For the parents' highest educational attainment variable, the computed t-value is 0.333, with a p-value of 0.742, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in making inferences when grouped and compared according to parents' highest educational attainment" is accepted.

For the average family monthly income variable, the computed t-value is -0.208, with a p-value of 0.837, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in making inferences when grouped and compared according to family monthly income" is accepted.

For the variable of the number of siblings, the computed t-value is 1.179, with a p-value of 0.249, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in making inferences when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings" is accepted.

The data revealed the number of siblings had the lowest p-value when making inferences. Learners from families with multiple siblings may encounter obstacles in resource competitiveness, less personalized attention from parents, and more distractions during study time – all of which might negatively affect learning and making inferences. Thus, teachers may play an essential role in boosting each learner's learning capacity by making them feel like they belong or are part of the group and engaging them in enjoyable activities to connect.

The study of Volkmar et al. (2014) supported the idea that interventions that increase environmental quality and child-caregiver interaction are relevant to cognitive development.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Drawing Conclusions when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Table 9

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Drawing Conclusions when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	20	52.00	-1.903	0.067		Not Significant
	Female	14	67.86				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	20	53.00	-1.578	0.125	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	66.43				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	16	48.70	-2.236	0.033		Significant
	Higher	18	67.22				
Number of Siblings	Few	13	64.62	1.106	0.279		Not Significant
	Many	21	54.76				

Table 9 shows the statistics on the significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in concluding when grouped and compared according to sex. As shown in Table 11, for variable sex, the computed t-value is -1.903 with a p-value of 0.067, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level and thus interpreted as "no significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in concluding when grouped and compared according to sex" is accepted.

For the parents' highest educational attainment variable, the computed t-value is -1.578, with a p-value of 0.125, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in concluding when grouped and compared according to parents' highest educational attainment" is accepted.

However, for the average family monthly income variable, the computed t-value is -2.236, with a p-value of 0.033, which is less than the 0.05 level and is thus interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in concluding when grouped and compared according to family monthly income" is not accepted.

For the variable of the number of siblings, the computed t-value is 1.106, with a p-value of 0.279, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in concluding when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings" is accepted.

This implies that learners' reading comprehension skills vary, as assessed by the respondents, compared to the average family monthly income. When comparing the results according to sex, the parents' highest educational attainment and the number of siblings did not vary. This is because families with higher incomes can provide insights into various aspects of a family's life that influence the interpretation of information or events. A closer examination of the data revealed that the average family income had the lowest p-value for making conclusions. The average family income significantly influences students' learning since a more considerable family income often gives better access to resources such as books, educational materials, and tutoring. Teacher support is vital in this scenario, as it provides them with enough reading materials, exciting activities, and differentiated instructions and engages them in peer tutoring.

Lin and Lv (2017) stressed that family income significantly impacts children's education level, and rising family income can improve their education level.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Sequencing Events when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Table 10
Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Sequencing Events when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	20	18.00	-1.882	0.071		Not Significant
	Female	14	29.29				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	20	16.50	-2.578	0.016	0.05	Significant
	Higher	14	31.43				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	16	18.13	-1.448	0.157		Not Significant
	Higher	18	26.67				
Number of Siblings	Few	13	27.69	1.240	0.229		Not Significant
	Many	21	19.52				

Table 10 shows the statistics on the significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in sequencing events when grouped and compared according to sex. As shown in Table 12, for variable sex, the computed t-value is -1.882 with a p-value of 0.071, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level and thus interpreted as "no significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in sequencing events when grouped and compared according to sex" is accepted.

However, for the parents' highest educational attainment variable, the computed t-value is -2.578, with a p-value of 0.016, which is less than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "significant". Therefore, the level of the

hypothesis that “there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in sequencing events when grouped and compared according to parents’ highest educational attainment” is not accepted.

For the average family monthly income variable, the computed t-value is -1.448, with a p-value of 0.157, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that “there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in sequencing events when grouped and compared according to family monthly income” is accepted. For the number of siblings, the computed t-value is 1.240, with a p-value of 0.229, which is greater than the 0.05 level and, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that “there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in sequencing events when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings” is accepted.

This implies that sequencing events learners' reading comprehension skills vary as assessed by the respondents when compared according to the parents’ highest educational attainment. Compared to sex, the average family's monthly income and the number of siblings did not vary. This is because parents with higher educational attainment are more likely to engage in literacy-related activities at home, such as reading to their children, discussing stories, and modeling comprehension strategies, and this early exposure to a literacy-rich environment can support the development of sequencing skills.

Looking deeper into the data from the area sequencing events, the parents' highest educational attainment had the lowest p-value. Most respondents coming from the family have lower educational attainment. Lower educational attainment might restrict children's exposure to literacy-rich contexts and explicit training in sequencing abilities, affecting their capacity to properly arrange and interpret chronological events. Teacher and parent constant communication, meetings, parent conferences, and home visitations are essential.

Chen et al. (2018) found that parents' educational attainment, parenting methods, and the parent-child connection impacted academic achievement and cognitive development.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Table 11

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Comprehension Skills in Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary when grouped and compared according to the Abovementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	20	2.00	-0.098	0.923	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	14	2.14				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	20	1.50	-0.907	0.374	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	2.86				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	16	1.88	-0.244	0.809	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	18	2.22				
Number of Siblings	Few	13	3.08	1.143	0.261	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	21	1.43				

Table 11 shows the statistics on the significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary when grouped and compared according to sex. As shown in Table 13, for variable sex, the computed t-value is -0.098 with a p-value of 0.923, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level and thus interpreted as “no significant.” Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that “there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary when grouped and compared according to sex” is accepted.

For the parents’ highest educational attainment variable, the computed t-value is -0.907, with a p-value of 0.374, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that “there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary when grouped and compared according to parents’ highest educational attainment” is accepted.

For the average family monthly income variable, the computed t-value is -0.244, with a p-value of 0.809, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that “there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying unfamiliar

vocabulary when grouped and compared according to family monthly income" is accepted. For the variable of the number of siblings, the computed t-value is 1.143, with a p-value of 0.261, which is greater than the 0.05 level and, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the level of the hypothesis that "there are no significant differences in the level of reading comprehension skills in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings" is accepted.

The results imply that in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary learners' reading comprehension skills, the respondents did not vary regardless of their sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and number of siblings. This is because a child's ability to identify unfamiliar vocabulary is primarily influenced by their cognitive skills, language development, and exposure to rich and varied vocabulary.

However, when analyzing the data to recognize unfamiliar vocabulary, the variable number of siblings has the lowest p-value among the number of siblings. Parents with more prominent families may need more time or resources to engage in activities that enhance vocabulary development, such as reading books, and less time to focus interactions on vocabulary development. Teachers can offer strategies to the parents by giving informal sessions, providing reading materials, mentoring and coaching, and constant home visitations.

Holzinger et al. (2020) stated that children from more prominent families tended to have lower vocabulary scores than those from smaller families. Additionally, larger family size may be associated with reduced opportunities for language exposure and vocabulary growth.

Conclusions

Based on the preceding findings of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions: As no two students are alike, the learning styles of students may vary from one another, which affects the learners' reading comprehension skills. On the other hand, sex is not considered a predictor in all areas: identifying the main idea or noting details, answering direct recall questions, making inferences, drawing conclusions, sequencing events, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. The learners' reading comprehension skills are not affected by their sex because the abilities of males and females may vary. On the other hand, a student's reading comprehension is impacted by their parents' most significant level of education, average family monthly income, and number of siblings since parents' reading encouragement is crucial to helping their kids develop their minds. Parental education levels have a significant impact on students' reading abilities. Low-income families can only support their children's education if they prioritize meeting their families' basic needs over purchasing educational supplies. As a result, children have less access to gadgets and other reading materials. Students from more prominent families face rivalry and competition in various areas, such as money and resources, and they must work for themselves rather than prioritize their education.

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